

Short communication

First record of the genus *Milesia* (Dip.: Syrphidae: Eristalinae) from Iran

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چکیده

با نمونه‌برداری از منطقه جنگلی حسین‌آباد استان قزوین، نمونه‌ای از جنس *Milesia* Latreille جمع‌آوری و با نام علمی *Milesia semiluctifera* (Villers, 1789) تشخیص داده شد. این اولین گزارش از جنس و گونه مذکور از ایران می‌باشد.

The genus *Milesia* Latreille (Dip.: Eristalinae: Milesiini) is one of the largest genera of flower flies. The members of the genus, with more than 80 species, mimic social wasps. Although the genus occurs in all continents, the majority of species are known from the Oriental region where 62 species have been recorded so far (Peck, 1988; Hippa, 1990). This genus can be recognized by the combination of following characters: postpronotal lobe hairy, arista and eye bare, R_{4+5} straight, cross vein $r-m$ oblique within apical half of discal cell, cell r_1 closed (Speight, 2010).

Hippa (1990) revised the genus *Milesia* worldwide and described 28 new species from the oriental region. He wrote a key to the species of the genus and defined new taxonomical characters (e.g. the shape of spermathecae) for male and female terminalia.

He recognized 23 species-groups in *Milesia*, of which seven species-groups, containing 13 species, exist in the Palaearctic region. These species-groups are as follows: *apsycta*, *crabroniformis*, *ferruginosa*, *fissipennis*, *semifulva*, *semiluctifera* and *undulata*.

Later, Cheng (2003) established six new synonymies, provided a key to Chinese species of the genus and recorded *Milesia variegata* Brunetti from China. Saleem *et al.* (2001) recorded two species of *Milesia*, *M. sexmaculata* Brunetti and *M. verticalis* Brunetti, from Pakistan. Dousti & Hayat (2006) authored the first catalogue of Syrphidae in Iran.

Here the genus *Milesia* is newly recorded from Iran. The collected specimen is keyed to the following species in Hippa (1990).

Fig. 1. *Milesia semiluctifera*: (a) head (lateral view), (b) abdomen (dorsal view), (c) wing, (d) pleura, (e) thorax (dorsal view).

- *Milesia semiluctifera* (Villers, 1789)

Material examined – 1 ♂, Hossein-abad forest, Taron region, Ghazvin, N 36°33' E 40°16', 1500 m., 3.vii.2012, swept on Umbellifera, leg. Babak Gharali.

Diagnosis – This species is easily distinguished from the closely related species *Milesia tadjikorum* Peck & Hippa by coloration of mesonotum and pleura (fig. 1). In *M. semiluctifera*, anepisternum and katapisternum

have yellow marks (lacking in *M. tadjikorum*) (Hippa, 1990).

Distribution – According to Hippa (1990), this species occurs in Turkey and the southeast of the Palaearctic region. The current finding expands the distribution of *M. semiluctifera* to the western parts of the Palaearctic region.

References

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